

The use of the thermophysical methods for silicate glasses

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ABSTRACT

In the field of glass structure and properties investigation, thermodilatometric measurements are mainly used to determine the glass transition temperature T_g and the coefficients of thermal expansion of the glass, α_g , and the metastable glass-forming melt, α_m . The coefficients of thermal expansion are determined from the slopes of the linear parts of the thermodilatometric curve below (α_g) and above (α_m) the temperature T_g . The temperature T_g is determined from the intersection point of the linear portions [1-9]. In order to obtain a longer linear portion of the curve above the glass transition temperature, measurements are made at higher temperatures. However, at a temperature of approx. (30-50) °C above the temperature T_g , the vertical arrangement of the dilatometer deforms the sample by the viscous flow and the peak is observed on the curve followed by a significant decrease in the sample height. Another field of application of thermodilatometric (thermomechanical) measurements in glass examination is the study of volume relaxation in the glass transition region, where the hysteresis thermodilatometric loops measured at a combination of different heating and cooling rates are analyzed. In this case too, the temperature must not reach the viscosity area at which the sample deforms by the viscous flow and produces a local maximum. For these reasons, in practice, thermodilatometric measurements in which the sample has been deformed by the viscous flow are referred to as "failed". If there is only a slight deformation by the viscous flow (without the formation of a local maximum), volume relaxation can be described by a model including the viscous flow (Fig. 1) [5-9].

Fig. 1: Volume relaxation model with viscous flow deformation (experiment - points).

The aim of this paper is to propose a method that in case of "failed" thermodilatometric curves, it would be possible to determine the thermal expansion of metastable melt and possibly viscosity as a function of local maximum temperature T_m from heating rate q ($q = dT / dt$) and the axial load on the sample, σ consisting of the sum of the net mass contribution of the sample m_{gl} and the added

mass m_{ad} :

$$\sigma = \frac{m_{ad} + m_{gl}/2}{S} g \quad (1)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration and S the cross-section of the prism sample. The local maximum temperature T_m is determined by the equation of the rate of increase of the sample height l :

$$\frac{dl}{l_0} = d\varepsilon = \alpha_m dT = \alpha_m q dt \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} = \dot{\varepsilon} = \alpha_m q \quad (3)$$

and the rate of decreasing its height

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = \frac{\sigma}{3\eta(T_m)} = \frac{\sigma}{3 \exp\left(A + \frac{B}{T_m}\right)} \quad (4)$$

where l_0 is the height at time $t = 0$, η is the viscosity and A and B are parameters of the Andrade viscosity equation [1-3].

If the temperature dependence of viscosity (ie values A and B) is known, the coefficient of thermal expansion of the metastable melt can be obtained as a slope of the linear dependence of Y on q :

$$Y(q) = \frac{\sigma}{3\eta[T_m(q)]} = \alpha_m q \quad (5)$$

If the temperature dependence of the viscosity is unknown, we can adjust Equation (5) to:

$$\ln(\sigma/3\alpha_m) - \ln(q_i) = A + \frac{B}{T_m(q_i)} \quad (6)$$

respectively

$$\ln q = K - B \left(\frac{1}{T_m(q)} \right) = K - Bx \quad (7)$$

where $x = 1/T_m(q)$ and $K = \ln(\sigma/3\alpha_m) - A$. In this case, we obtain the value of K as the segment and the value of B as the slope of the dependence of $\ln q$ from x .

We can roughly estimate the value of A based on the relationship:

$$\ln[\eta(T_g)/\text{Pa.s}] = A + B/T_g = \ln 10^{12} \Rightarrow A = \ln 10^{12} - B/T_g \quad (8)$$

where T_g is determined from a cooling thermodilatometric curve measured at a cooling rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Keywords: thermodilatometric, glass, Andrade viscosity equation.

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